

Application of American Theories for Eventuality Types to the Description of Bulgarian Verbs

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Abstract: This study aims to demonstrate the applicability of various linguistic tests originally developed for English to distinguish states, activities, accomplishments, and achievements in Bulgarian. The study begins with a brief overview of Vendler's aspectual classes and the lexicogrammatical category of verb aspect in Bulgarian. Using some selected linguistic tests, we show that the main reason why some of the existing tests cannot be applied directly to Bulgarian is the verb aspect inherent in every Bulgarian verb. Finally, we conclude how Bulgarian perfective and imperfective verbs refer to different eventuality types.

Keywords: aspectual classes, eventuality types, Bulgarian verb aspect

Introduction

Numerous scholars have proposed linguistic tests based on Zeno Vendler's work to detect aspectual classes (also known as eventuality types) (Vendler 1967): states, activities, accomplishments, and achievements. While such tests have been extensively discussed and extended for English and some other Slavic languages, attention has currently shifted to Bulgarian, focusing on states (Koeva et al. 2022) and activities.

This study aims to demonstrate the applicability of several well-known linguistic tests, originally developed for English, to the distinction between states, activities, accomplishments, and achievements in Bulgarian. We begin with a brief presentation of the characteristics of Vendler's aspectual classes and the lexicogrammatical category of verb aspect in Bulgarian. Using carefully selected linguistic tests, we show that the main reason why some of the existing linguistic tests cannot be applied directly to Bulgarian is the category of verb aspect with which each Bulgarian verb is characterised. Finally, we draw some conclusions about how the Bulgarian perfective and imperfective verbs correspond to the different eventuality types.

Aspectual Classes in Brief

According to Comrie (1976: 3), who relies on an earlier definition, aspect refers to the "different ways of viewing the internal temporal constituency of a situation." Linguists distinguish between lexical, grammatical, and lexicogrammatical aspects, depending on the level at which the "internal temporal constituency" is rendered. Zeno Vendler's classification, which determines states, activities, accomplishments, and achievements, is usually referred to as lexical aspect.

Vendler's classification has been followed by various more detailed descriptions of event types (Mourelatos 1978; Dowty 1979; Bach 1986; etc.). Most of the outstanding researchers working on this topic have worked at American universities, including Zeno Vendler, who was born and died in Hungary but worked at many universities in North America (the United States and Canada). Below is a summary of the main characteristics of the verb aspectual classes that recur in many works.

The basic aspectual distinction is between states and non-states. States are events (eventualities) that do not involve change: *hate, know, believe, be blond*. Non-states are events (eventualities) that involve a change: *run, walk, sleep, reach, win, break, hit*. The associated aspectual characteristics are: stativity and its opposite, dynamicity, where the predicates for state are +stative and –dynamic and the predicates for activity, accomplishment, and achievement are –stative and +dynamic.

Some verbs (activities) describe events that take time but have no inherent temporal endpoint; such events could go on indefinitely, at least if there are no real-world constraints or conventions: *run, walk*.

There are some verbs (accomplishments) that also describe events that take time, but these events have an inherent endpoint, also called “culmination” or “telos”, at which a final state occurs: *building a house*. In contrast to activities, accomplishments offer a more detailed description of the internal temporal structure of a situation than activities. For example, *approaching the bench* describes an action with a clear beginning, course, and endpoint. The associated aspectual characteristics are: **non-telicity** and its opposite, **telicity**. The predicates for state and activity are –telic (or atelic), while the predicates for accomplishment and achievement are +telic.

Some verbs (achievements), such as *break*, describe punctual events; they describe the point in time at which a transition to a result state takes place. The associated aspectual characteristics are: non-durativity (momentary) and its opposite, durativity. The state, activity, and accomplishment predicates are +durative and –momentary, while the achievement predicates are –durative and +momentary (punctual).

Some verbs (semelfactives), such as *hit*, describe punctual events (Engelberg 2000), but as activities, there is no resulting state that follows. Semelfactives are thus characterised as +dynamic, –telic and +momentary. However, many aspect classifications only recognise four aspectual classes, the Vendlerian classes, and subsume semelfactives under achievements.

In some languages, there are also grammatical markers that distinguish these aspectual classes; for example, states and achievements in English cannot normally be used with the progressive (**I am knowing the answer* and **I am winning the contest*), whereas activities and accomplishments can (*I am walking* and *I am approaching the bench*).

H. Filip (2012) gives an overview of the difference between the lexical and the grammatical aspect as well as the related concepts and terms.

Bulgarian Lexicogrammatical Aspect in Brief

The Slavic languages have a sophisticated system for marking the difference between the perfective and imperfective verb aspect. In Bulgarian, it is assumed that aspect is a lexicogrammatical category, as verbs with different aspects are different lexical units created by word formation (Andreychin 1944: 137,193; Kutsarov 2007: 546; Nitsolova 2008: 247; etc.). The following is a brief description of the characteristics of Bulgarian perfective and imperfective verbs, which are described in more detail in many works.

Bulgarian perfective and imperfective verbs typically show clear morphological differences. Aspectual derivation in Bulgarian involves two main processes: perfectivisation and imperfectivisation, which can occur separately or together. Certain verbs have a morphologically non-derived imperfective form (*imperfectiva tantum*) and can form perfective counterparts through prefixation. Conversely, perfective verbs can become imperfective through suffixation, a process known as secondary imperfectivisation. As a result, many Bulgarian verbs have aspect triplets.

- 1.a. *пия* imperfective 'drink'
- 1.b. *изпия* perfective 'drink up'
- 1.c. *изпивам* imperfective 'to be drinking up'

A smaller group of verbs are morphologically non-derived perfective verbs (*perfectiva tantum*), which produce imperfective counterparts through suffixation. Both non-derived perfective and derived imperfective verbs can form new prefixed verbs, whereby the lexicogrammatical aspect of the original verb is retained.

- 2.a. *скача*, perfective 'jump'
- 2.b. *скачам*, imperfective 'to be jumping'
- 3.a. *скача*, perfective 'jump'
- 3.b. *подскача*, perfective 'jump up'
- 4.a. *скачам*, imperfective 'to be jumping'
- 4.b. *подскачам*, imperfective 'to be jumping up'

For the analyses we have carried out, the type of the source verb is important in the derivation, since not only can the derived verb change its aspect, but it can also take on some of the aspectual characteristics of the source verb. If the derivation concerns a primary verb in the imperfective aspect, this leads to a change in the aspect (both the lexical meaning and the associated morphological and syntactic features). If the derivation concerns a primary verb in the perfective aspect, this may or may not lead to a shift in the verb aspect. If the derivation is applied to a derived perfective verb, this leads to a change in the verb aspect, although some features of the perfective aspect are retained. If the derivation is applied to a derived imperfective verb, the aspect does not change, only the lexical meaning of the verb.

Linguistic Tests

A variety of diagnostic tests have been proposed to differentiate between the aspectual classes. Most of them are summarised by Dowty (1979: 60). The tests aim to distinguish between states and activities, on the one hand, and accomplishments and achievements, on the other. Some tests developed for English may not apply to Bulgarian due to the inherent differences in the expression of the Slavic verb aspect.

We have selected some tests that are relevant to the distinction between states, activities, accomplishments, and achievements.

Test with *force, persuade*

States cannot be complements of *force, persuade*, etc., whereas **activities** and **accomplishments** can be (Dowty 1979: 55)¹.

5.a. **John forced Harry to know the answer.* state

5.b. *John persuaded Harry to run.* activity

5.c. *John forced Harry to build a house.* accomplishment

The test works for Bulgarian. The translations of the examples in 5. are included in 6.

6.a. **Джон принуди Хари да **знае** отговора.* state, imperfective verb

6.b. *Джон убеди Хари да **тича**.* activity, imperfective verb

6.c. *Джон накара / принуди Хари да **построи** къща.* accomplishment, perfective verb

State verbs such as *sit, stand, lie, wait, and sleep* fulfil all the criteria for Davidsonian eventualities such as activities: they are perceptible and localised in space and time. In contrast, state verbs such as *know, weigh, own, and resemble* (Kimian states) do not fulfil any of these criteria (Maienborn (2007: 3–6): Kimian states are not accessible to direct perception and have no location in space, but can be localised in time. For this reason, verbs such as *лежа* ‘lie’ are also combined with *force* and *persuade*.

7.a. *Убеждавам детето да **лежи** на леглото, докато заспи.* Davidsonian state, imperfective verb

7.b. *I persuade the child to **lie** on the bed until it falls asleep.*

Tests with the expressions *in an hour / for an hour*

The following test can distinguish between states and activities vs. accomplishments and achievements.

¹The achievements were not included in the Dowty test.

State and **activity** verbs do not occur with the expression *in an hour*, but verbs for **accomplishments** and **achievements** do (Dowty 1979: 60).

- 8.a. **John knows French in an hour.* state
- 8.b. **John runs in an hour.* activity
- 8.c. *She gave birth in an hour.* accomplishment
- 8.d. *The lamp **blinked** in a second.* achievement

The test works for Bulgarian. The translations of the examples in 7. are included in 8.

- 9.a. **Джон **знае** френски за един час.* state, imperfective verb
- 9.b. **Джон **тича** за един час.* activity, imperfective verb
- 9.c. *Тя **роди** за един час.* accomplishment, perfective verb
- 9.d. *Лампата **мигна** за секунда.* achievement, perfective verb

We can assume that the observation for Russian that primary imperfective verbs denote states and activities and primary perfective verbs denote accomplishments and achievements (Paducheva 2010: 107–108) applies to Bulgarian, as has already been shown (Коева 2021: 142–143). Since the test applied in English applies to activities and accomplishments as well as achievements, i.e. to situations that are not static, the expression of the predicate in Bulgarian with a non-static imperfective or perfective verb has no influence on the applicability of the test, or the test is not influenced by the lexicogrammatical aspect of the verb.

The other test with a temporal expression states that **state**, **activity**, and **accomplishment** verbs occur with the expression *for an hour*, which means that they occur at any point in the hour, but verbs for **achievements** do not (Dowty 1979: 60).

- 10.a. *For four years, John **has lived** in London.* state
- 10.b. *John **walked** for an hour.* activity
- 10.c. *They **painted** the picture for an hour.* accomplishment
- 10.d. **They **arrived** for an hour.* achievement (Unacceptable is the meaning that it took them an hour to arrive, as opposed to the meaning that they arrived to stay an hour.)

The translations of the examples from 9. into Bulgarian can be found in 10.

- 11.a. *От четири години Джон **живее** в Лондон.* state, imperfective verb
- 11.b. *Джон **вървя** в продължение на час.* activity, imperfective verb
- 11.c.a. *Те **нарисуваха** картината в продължение на един час.* accomplishment, derived perfective verb
- 11.c.b. *Те **рисуваха** картината в продължение на един час.* activity, imperfective verb
- 11.d.a. **Те **пристигнаха** в продължение на час.* achievement, derived perfective verb
- 11.d.b. *Те **пристигаха** в продължение на час.* activity, derived imperfective verb

States and activities are translated with imperfective Bulgarian verbs. However, in a limited context, verbs that express accomplishments or achievements in English can be translated into Bulgarian with both (derived) imperfective and perfective verbs. Taking into account the direction of derivation between perfective and imperfective verbs, we can draw the following conclusions: Derived perfective verbs are either accomplishments or achievements and derived imperfective verbs are activities if the verb from which they are formed is also imperfective.

Aspectual Shifts

It has been established that the same verb in English can switch between different aspectual classes depending on the realisation of its arguments. The change from activity to accomplishment is observed, for example, in the manner of motion verbs, which are divided into two classes depending on whether they occur in their basic, undirected motion meaning or with a directed motion meaning (Rappaport, Hovav and Levin 1998).

12.a. *John runs*. activity

12.b. *John ran to the store*. accomplishment

M. Krifka (1989) and H. Verkuyl (1993) develop compositional analyses in which the aspectual class of the whole sentence is determined by the semantic nature of the verb, the properties of its arguments, and the way in which the verb is connected to its arguments. H. de Swart (1998) assumes that the aspectual class is determined at the predicate-argument level (eventuality description), that aspects are different ways of viewing the internal temporal constituents of a situation, and that the category of tense functions over all aspectual operators. In Bulgarian, an additional component, the lexicogrammatical aspect, should be taken into account when analysing the aspectual classes.

Conclusion

This brief analysis confirms that in Bulgarian, source verbs and derived verbs with different aspects can show different behaviours when they are subjected to linguistic tests for aspectual classes.

Non-derived imperfective verbs can express either a state or an activity. Imperfective verbs that are derived from imperfective source verbs can express activities. Imperfective verbs derived from perfective verbs can express accomplishments (or achievements). Perfective verbs can express either accomplishments or achievements, depending on the durability of the event.

Derived verbs can belong to different lexicogrammatical aspects and different eventuality types. This suggests that the meaning of grammatical markers, together with the lexical meaning conveyed by formative prefixes, plays an important role in determining their categorisation into the eventuality classes. In addition, verbs belonging to the same aspect pair may exhibit different aspectual behaviour.

Analysis of the linguistic tests for the differentiation of the aspectual classes in Bulgarian can contribute to a better understanding of the correspondence between the aspectual classes and the lexicogrammatical category of the verb aspect in Bulgarian.

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